

SmartCorners

D7.1

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (1)

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1 Executive Summary

As electric vehicles (EVs) gain traction, optimising their design and operation becomes crucial. In-wheel motors (IWMs) offer a promising solution, integrating powertrain, brake and suspension systems. Realising the full potential of IWMs leaves room for sophisticated control strategies to manage diverse vehicle functionalities. In this context, the EU-funded SmartCorners project will use artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning to revolutionise EVs by enhancing design, energy efficiency, user comfort and circularity. Specifically, the project will focus on skateboard-like chassis configurations and predictive thermal management. Accelerated by advanced simulation and validation, the project will reduce development time and cost, support Europe's competitive position in the EV industry and positively influence end-user acceptance of EVs in the future [1].

This deliverable summarises the communication, dissemination and exploitation plans of the SmartCorners consortium after six (6) months of project execution. An introduction in Chapter 2, specifies the timely focus on communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in the project. Chapter 0 presents the Key Exploitable Results (KER)-oriented understanding of communication, dissemination and exploitation and the methodology pursued towards planning and monitoring the project's dissemination and exploitation activities. The project's stakeholder engagement strategy is shortly introduced in Chapter 4, presenting an essential multiplication factor regarding dissemination and providing a successful path for exploitation. Chapter 5 presents the corporate identity, encompassing the visual identity strongly influencing communication material and templates for project execution. The communication channels, created by the project or accessible through networks, are described in Chapter 6 along with communication material and the communication planning. Initial dissemination and exploitation plans, that will be fed through the methodology presented in Chapter 0, are described in Chapters 7 and 8. Section 9 concludes this deliverable.

2 Introduction

The SmartCorners consortium follows broad and targeted communication measures to be realised through the different channels shown in Figure 1. These channels have proven effective in previous projects involving consortium members (Horizon 2020 projects EVC1000¹ and XILforEV²). Moreover, a similar strategy is being applied in the recently funded Horizon Europe projects HighScape³, HiPE⁴ and EM-TECH⁵. During the first six (6) months of the project execution, a clear focus was set on setting the basis for communication, such as developing the visual identity, establishing communication channels and creating communication material and finetuning the stakeholder engagement strategy. The planning for dissemination and early consideration of exploitation is being started and reflected in this deliverable.

Figure 1: SmartCorners Outreach

Ultimately, the activities are planned to achieve the following objectives as presented in Table 1.

¹ <https://www.evc1000.eu/en>

² <https://xil.cloud>

³ <https://highscape.eu>

⁴ <https://www.hipeproject.eu>

⁵ <https://emtechproject.eu>

Objectives
monthly update of the SmartCorners news on the website
Two project publications per year
3 publications per year in national newspapers/magazines
1 publication per year in EU public journals
at least 2 TV reports (1 on a regional and 1 on a pan-European TV company)
annual SmartCorners presentations at open days in each participating organisation
> 500 direct LinkedIn followers
> 3 presentations/year at conferences
> 3 co-organized special sessions
> 6 journal publications in recognised academic journals in the relevant areas (open access)
> 2 actions (e.g. as news publications, webinars) for each target society (interaction with professional societies)
2 actions as news publications or webinars for each target society (advocate ecosystem platforms)
at least one patent application for each WP2-5 dedicated to the SmartCorners technologies.
six PhDs trained by participating universities (POLITO, TUIL) in SmartCorners topics.

Table 1: Objectives for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

3 Methodology

The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in SmartCorners are understood as supporting each other to benefit the project's impact. Moving further from the commonly known picture, showing communication, dissemination and exploitation in three distinctive roles, we adopted the integrative aspect as displayed in a recent webinar from the IPR Helpdesk:

Figure 2: Three things to tell people about [2]

Content planning (see chapter 6.2.5) is therefore closely related to dissemination and future exploitation planning. It raises awareness among stakeholders and ultimately increases the project's impact. The activities follow a methodology currently developed and implemented in the project EM-TECH and summarised in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SmartCorners road to impact

3.1 Dissemination & Exploitation planning

To facilitate and support the impact generation and communications process, a Dissemination and Exploitation tracker has been established (following the methodology developed and implemented in EM-TECH), supporting the project's continuous dissemination and exploitation monitoring. In the following, extractions from this table are presented:

PUBLICATIONS																
Sequential-No.	KER/PO-No.	Lead partner	Author(s)	International co-authors	Title of publication	Type of publication	Journal, Conferences ... (Details)	Aim	DOI	Status	Date of publication	Involved project partner(s)	Access to background data ...	Link	Remarks	
PD-1																
PD-2																
PD-3																
PD-4																
PD-5																
PD-6																
PD-7																
PD-8																

PUBLIC EVENTS														
Sequential-No.	KER/PO-No.	Title of the event	Involved person(s)	Role(s) of project representative(s)	Type of public event	Target group	Date	Venue	Aim	Area of influence	Status	Access to background data ...	Remarks	
PE-1														
PE-2														
PE-3														
PE-4														
PE-5														
PE-6														
PE-7														
PE-8														

PATENTS													
Sequential-No.	KER/PO-No.	Area of Patent / Utility Model / IPR	Title of the Patent / Utility Model / IPR Incl. Designation No.	Patent / Utility Model / IPR applied for	Patent / Utility Model / IPR granted	Inventor(s)	Patent / Utility Model / IPR holder	Involved project partner(s)	Status	Joint patent	Remarks		
PAT-1													
PAT-2													
PAT-3													
PAT-4													
PAT-5													
PAT-6													
PAT-7													
PAT-8													

PROTOTYPES, DEMONSTRATORS, PRODUCTS, PROCESSES, AND SERVICES											
Sequential-No.	KER/PO-No.	Title	Type	Responsible person	Involved project partner(s)	Date	Status	Access to background data	Joint prototype, demonstrator, product, process, or service	Remarks	
PDP-1											
PDP-2											
PDP-3											
PDP-4											
PDP-5											
PDP-6											
PDP-7											
PDP-8											

Figure 4: Dissemination and exploitation monitoring

4 Stakeholder Engagement

The stakeholder engagement strategy has been initiated to guarantee proper interaction among various stakeholders from different group fields, benefit from their knowledge, and match the defined project outcomes with the market needs and identified expectations. This strategy is currently being developed under close collaboration within Work Package 7. This deliverable provides a brief and initial glimpse into the stakeholder engagement strategy and the expected benefits. Critical element of the stakeholder engagement is the feedback loop into the SmartCorners vehicle concepts to ensure innovations pursued in the project are use-oriented and deliver on societal perspectives.

The stakeholder analysis has led to a number of stakeholders, described in D1.1 [3], being grouped together to approach them with appropriate engagement activities and assign them to potential use cases. A four-step process (Figure 5) has been developed for executing the stakeholder needs assessment and is in the initial execution stage.

Figure 5: 4 step stakeholder engagement process

In-depth information on these topics will be given in the deliverables D1.2, D7.3 and D7.4.

5 Corporate Identity

Already at the project's start, a visual identity was created and aligned between the project partners. Consequently, it has been introduced into D8.1, the Project Handbook and provided as guidelines for "visual identity".

5.1 Visual Identity

5.1.1 Project Logo

The SmartCorners logo was already created during the proposal preparation.

Figure 6: SmartCorners logo

The SmartCorners logo reflects the architecture of the wheel corner as an independent vehicle unit. The central circle is for the in-wheel motor, i.e. two actuators: one for traction and one for braking simultaneously. Four links connected to the circle represent the four remaining systems/actuators:

- For active steering
- Active suspension
- Active camber
- and Active toe.

Small circles at the ends of these four links represent small motors for actuators. The font used in the logo to include the project acronym has been chosen to represent streets in future content production.

To facilitate the further strategic use of the project logo on different backgrounds, several variations have been developed, all following the colour palette defined:

Figure 7: SmartCorners Logo variations

For reduced space application, the icon is created also as a single graphic:

Figure 8: Symbolic logo variations

5.1.2 Colour Palette

A colour palette for the creation of all deliverables and communication activities is established, derived from the project logo.

Figure 9: SmartCorners colour palette

5.1.3 Fonts

Fonts selected for written products of the SmartCorners are “Poppins” for headers and “Calibri” for text.

5.1.4 Supporting Icons

To further support the visual communication of the SmartCorners project, the following supporting icons, available in the colour palette of the project, have been established to highlight the areas of (1) In Wheel Concept, (2) Artificial Intelligence, (3) Sustainability and (4) User Centric as displayed in Table 2.

In Wheel Concept	Artificial Intelligence	Sustainability	User Centric

Table 2: SmartCorners supporting icons

5.2 Project Templates

Following the visual identity as described in chapter 5.1, project templates for various applications have been created and are explained in the following.

5.2.1 Deliverables

Figure 10: Deliverable front page

Figure 11: Deliverable final page

The inner part of the deliverable is providing guidance on the formatting of figures, tables, body text, indexes and bullet point / numbered lists.

5.2.2 Presentations

A presentation template has been created to facilitate the uniform appearance of the project in all meetings and during events:

Figure 12: PPT Template title page

Figure 13: PPT Template content

Figure 14: PPT Template final page

5.2.3 Minutes of Meeting and Participant List

The project internal communication is following the visual identity as well, leading to template for minutes of meeting and participant lists as follows.

A template for meeting minutes. At the top left is the SmartCorners logo. To its right is the title "Minutes of Meeting". Below the logo is a small square icon with a plus sign. The form contains fields for "Date:", "Time:", and "Subject:". Below these is a "Participants:" section with a table-like structure. The first row has headers "[Name of Participant]" and "[Abbr]". There are two columns of horizontal lines for data entry. Below the participants section is a large rectangular box labeled "Executive Summary:". At the bottom center of the page is the word "confidential", and at the bottom right is "Page 1 of 3".

Participants:	
[Name of Participant]	[Abbr]
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____

Figure 15: Template minutes of meeting

6.1.1 Project Leaflet

Facts

The project is funded under Horizon Europe, Call HORIZON-CLS-2023-D5-01-01. SmartCorners started on Jan 01, 2024 with a project duration of 36 months and is coordinated by AVL DiTest GmbH, Austria. The consortium is composed by 11 partners from 5 European countries at total costs € 6 317 719,99.

SmartCorners is an active member of the E-VOLVE Cluster and selected under the "Towards zero emission road transport" partnership (Z2EVO).

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USER-CENTRED OPTIMAL DESIGN OF ELECTRIC VEHICLE WITH SMART E-CORNERS

Revolutionising electric vehicles

As electric vehicles (EVs) gain traction, optimising their design and operation becomes crucial. In-wheel motors (IWMs) offer a promising solution, integrating powertrain, brake and suspension systems. Realising the full potential of IWMs leaves room for sophisticated control strategies to manage diverse vehicle functionalities. In this context, the EU-funded SmartCorners project will use AI and machine learning to revolutionise EVs by enhancing design, energy management, user comfort and recycling processes. Specifically, the project will focus on skateboard-like chassis configurations and predictive thermal management. Accelerated by advanced simulation and validation, the project will reduce development time and cost, support Europe's competitive position in the EV industry and positively influence end user acceptance of EVs in the future.

Project Consortium

Objectives

- Accelerated design and testing methodologies of adaptable, efficient, right-sized, flexible and user-centric smart corner systems (SCS) based on in-wheel powertrains
- Holistic thermal and passenger comfort management
- Predictive, user-centric, AI- and model-based control solutions for SCS equipped EVs
- New series of scalable and flexible SCS for next-generation EVs

Results

- DT Methodology of User-centred EV design
- Smart EV Optimal Operation Management
- Wheel Corner Design Global EV Motion Control
- User-centred Thermal and Cabin Comfort Management

Figure 17: Project Leaflet

6.1.2 Roll-Up

The graphic is a vertical roll-up with a dark blue background and yellow circular accents. At the top left, a circular inset shows a close-up of a car wheel with a multi-spoke alloy rim and a tire tread. Below this, the SmartCorners logo is displayed, consisting of a white icon of a central circle with three lines extending outwards, followed by the text "SmartCorners" in a bold, yellow, sans-serif font. Underneath the logo, the project title "User-centred Optimal Design of Electric Vehicle with Smart E-Corners" is written in a smaller, yellow, sans-serif font. Below the title, the website address "www.smartcorners.eu" is shown in a white, sans-serif font. At the bottom of the graphic, there is a circular inset showing a futuristic, sleek electric car in motion on a road at dusk or dawn, with light trails from other vehicles. In the bottom left corner, there is a QR code. In the bottom center, there is the European Union flag logo with the text "Funded by the European Union" below it. In the bottom right corner, there is a small block of text: "Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101138110. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

SmartCorners

User-centred Optimal
Design of Electric Vehicle
with Smart E-Corners

www.smartcorners.eu

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Figure 18: SmartCorners Roll-Up

6.1.4 Project Video

A first project video has been prepared to describe the overall concept of the SmartCorners project and introduce the project to a wider audience. The project video lasting about 2 minutes is composed of 5 episodes representing:

	<p>Episode 0: Thumbnail / Opener – following the SmartCorners Visual Identity</p>
	<p>Episode 1: presenting the overall motivation of electric vehicles of the future to be more user-centred and purpose-oriented</p>
	<p>Episode 2: Introducing the distributed vehicle architecture as possible solution</p>
	<p>Episode 3: Introducing the SmartCorners approach with the respective innovations</p>

	Episode 4: Presenting the partners
	Episode 5: concluding with the overall objectives to be achieved by the project.

Table 3: Project video screenplay

At the time of writing of this deliverable, the project video is being finalised with review by the project consortium being started, soon. When agreed and finalised, the video will be published on the SmartCorners website and distributed through the relevant communication channels.

6.2 Communication Channels

6.2.1 SmartCorners Website

The SmartCorners website, as already introduced in Deliverable D8.1, is accessible under www.smartcorners.eu and is designed to provide an overview of the project, the partners and the objectives. Additionally, it has a section on news and updates to be fed into social media.

Figure 20: SmartCorners Homepage

Figure 21: SmartCorners News Section

6.2.2 Zenodo

As part of our strategy towards open access, all public information is made available on Zenodo and linked to our project website / promoted on social media. A Zenodo Community⁶ was created at the start of the project and will host all open access information as they become available.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/smartcorners>

6.2.3 LinkedIn

The SmartCorners consortium has chosen to pursue social media via the LinkedIn network. LinkedIn is considered as the “B2B Network” among social media networks, with currently over 1 billion members in 200 countries and regions worldwide (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: LinkedIn members worldwide [4]

Looking closely at Europe, there are over 278 million members and over 67 million companies listed on LinkedIn. Based on the target audience to be reached and the social media activity of the project participants, the SmartCorners consortium strategically decided to stay with LinkedIn as the only social media channel instead of pursuing a multichannel strategy.

The LinkedIn channel for SmartCorners was established at the very beginning of the project and, until writing this deliverable, has attracted 105 followers and 7.377 impressions [5].

Figure 23: SmartCorners LinkedIn channel⁷

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/smartcorners>

6.2.4 E-VOLVE Cluster Channels

Being a member of the E-VOLVE cluster, the SmartCorners project can use the communication channels established by the cluster. The E-VOLVE cluster groups 8 finished projects (EVC1000, SELFIE, Multi-Moby, SYS2WHEEL, CEVOLVER, TELL, FITGEN and Achilles) and, 12 ongoing projects (RHODas, EM-TECH, HiPE, HighScape, SCAPE, POWERDRIVE, MAXIMA, VOLT CAR, EFFEREST, MINDED and HEFT) including SmartCorners. The communication channels established include:

- A website with continuous updates, accessible under www.evolvecluster.eu
- A LinkedIn channel⁸, at the point of writing this deliverable, counting 413 followers
- A Twitter channel⁹, at the point of writing this deliverable, counting 107 followers
- A quarterly Newsletter, available as PDF on the website and for the projects as well as published on LinkedIn, having 244 subscribers at the point of writing the deliverable
- A Zenodo community to spread the Newsletters, linking to the project communities as available

6.2.5 Content planning

A communication plan has been developed to centrally organise the content planning for the diverse communication channels. The plan is updated regularly and includes the scheduling of the communication activities as well as the content production items. The target set by the SmartCorners consortium is a monthly update of the SmartCorners news on the website, two project publications per year and > 500 direct LinkedIn followers.

Figure 24: Communication & Content Planning

⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/e-volve-cluster>

⁹ <https://x.com/EVOLVECluster>

Project participants have received guidelines on social media and a process to contribute to the content generation in D8.1 to support participants' social media activities to be reposted on the SmartCorners channel.

Figure 25: Partner and participant postings

7 Dissemination

SmartCorners follows a KER-oriented strategy towards dissemination (and exploitation) to ensure proper dissemination of the key exploitable results. The methodology to be pursued is presented in chapter 0. The following subsections describe the plans set by the consortium to pursue the dissemination activities and the relevant KPIs defined for these.

7.1 Project documentation

SmartCorners will deliver 32 deliverables, of which more than 40 % will be publicly available.

Figure 26: Confidentiality of SmartCorners deliverables

No.	Deliverable Content
D1.1	Report on SmartCorners technologies and user-centric vehicle control functions: overview of the smart corner technologies, incl. specifications and control system functions
D7.1	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan
D3.1	Design report on thermal and cabin comfort control: analysis of thermal system design and thermal system controller concepts. Decision based on cost, performance and complexity for the most promising concepts.
D7.2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan, detailing the CDE plans towards project end
D7.3	Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Report, documenting actions and results achieved by the engagement and promotion strategies (V1)
D5.1	Innovative predictive control solutions supported by fleet data: chassis controllers based on NMPC and NNMPC strategies, vertical tire force-vectoring control and wheel kinematic control algorithms, supported by off-board data, cloud computing and AI-based solutions (V1)
D1.4	Report on validated simulation models: simulation results for SmartCorners solutions
D2.3	Smart-e-corner components susp. arms and upright, ride quality control actuator, x-by-wire chassis control actuator, power electronics for suspension actuation systems)
D3.3	Report on final thermal and cabin comfort control; Document the final results of the controller's performance. Describe the limitations and how they can be addressed in future projects.
D4.4	Digital twin model of the EV with <i>SmartCorners</i> topology benchmark: A benchmark of the accuracy of the digital representation of the EV with <i>SmartCorners</i> topology on component and system levels, enabling performance analysis and optimisation of hardware and software.
D4.5	XIL Validation environment workflow: An agile model-based XIL validation workflow that improves execution time, reliability, repeatability, and cost-effectiveness for various stages of development and testing.
D5.4	Innovative predictive control solutions supported by fleet data: chassis controllers based on NMPC and NNMPC strategies, vertical tire force-vectoring control and wheel kinematic control algorithms, supported by off-board data, cloud computing and AI-based solutions (V2)
D6.3	Replication report: Report on replicability of smart corner concepts towards multiple vehicle segments
D7.4	Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Report, documenting actions and results achieved by the engagement and promotion strategies (V2)

Table 4: List of public deliverables

Public deliverables will be made available on Zenodo and linked to the project website and communicated via the communication channels established for the project and in cooperation with e.g. the E-VOLVE cluster and 2Zero.

7.2 Presentation at conferences

The SmartCorners consortium has selected some of the most important conferences in the field of electric vehicles where the project results can be presented in 2025 and 2026:

- IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference VPPS
- SAE World Automotive Congress
- Flanders Make Annual Symposium and Conference
- RTR (2026)
- TRA (2026)

Further events will be identified continuously by the partners with the target to achieve > 3 presentations/year, > 3 co-organized special sessions

7.3 Presentation in professional exhibitions

SmartCorners results will be presented in the second half of the project lifetime (2025 and 2026) at the EC's Transport Research Arena, International Test Expo, IAA Automotive Fair and other events.

In September 2024, the first representation of the SmartCorners concepts will take place at the IAA TRANSPORTATION 2024 with partner HER having a stand there (Hall 22):

“The motivation is to seed a vision of the future in how a futuristic steering axle design might look without the historic legacy of traditional methods and principles. The advantages are numerous in functionality, increased cabin or cargo space and vehicle dynamics. The rugged mechanical design is based on fundamental principles but the functionality is created by AI based robotics software. This is different than traditional thinking where functionality is created by mechanical design.

The Smart Corner project is adding an additional layer of possibilities (in wheel positioning like camber, toe) in an over-actuated vehicle. The stand will show a simplified steering actuator using variable wishbone arms that can vary trackwidth and steering direction.”

The stand will further be equipped with the SmartCorners Roll-Up, Leaflet and the project video displayed on the screen that will be available.

7.4 Publications in journals

It is planned to have > 6 journal publications in recognised academic journals in the relevant areas (open access):

- IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification
- IEEE Trans. On Industrial Electronics
- Open Research Europe

7.5 Interaction with professional societies

SmartCorners project partners are active in different professional societies and organisations. Consequently, they will leverage their experience to disseminate the SmartCorners project results to:

- Various working groups of IEEE
- SAE International¹⁰
- VDI¹¹
- UBIA¹²
- ANFIA ATA¹³

The target is to have > 2 actions (e.g. as news publications, webinars) for each target society

7.6 Advocate Ecosystem Platforms

These will include:

- BDVA¹⁴
- EPOSS¹⁵
- AIOTI¹⁶
- ERTRAC¹⁷
- EARPA¹⁸
- Other public funded projects under Horizon Europe (2ZERO¹⁹, E-VOLVE Cluster²⁰)

The target is to have > 2 actions as news publications or webinars for each target society.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, 5 projects from the E-VOLVE cluster (EM-TECH²¹, HighScape²², HiPE, SCAPE²³ and Powerdrive) have started cooperations with the Horizon Results Booster targeting an E-VOLVE Cluster webinar in autumn 2024. The SmartCorners consortium plans to participate to the open call for contributions thus participate to this webinar.

¹⁰ <https://www.sae.org>

¹¹ <https://www.vdi.de>

¹² <https://www.ubia.be/nl/english>

¹³ <https://www.fisita.org/directory/anfia-ata>

¹⁴ <https://bdva.eu>

¹⁵ <https://www.smart-systems-integration.org>

¹⁶ <https://aioti.eu>

¹⁷ <https://www.ertrac.org>

¹⁸ <https://www.earpa.eu>

¹⁹ <https://www.2zeroemission.eu>

²⁰ <https://evolvecluster.eu>

²¹ www.emtechproject.eu

²² www.highscape.eu

²³ <https://www.scapepower.eu>

8 Exploitation

SmartCorners will seek to achieve long-lasting impact in the way innovation is properly managed. To this end, the project will demonstrate four main exploitation models for the result:

- **Commercial exploitation model** monetises the project results for paid customers, complying with a licensing scheme, which will be defined in the business modelling. It is of interest mostly to the enterprise players (industrial partners and SMEs). SmartCorners will employ support services facilitated by the European Commission under initiatives like the [Horizon Results Booster](#) (e.g. ‘Business Plan Development’ and ‘Go To Market’ services), [Dealflow.eu](#) (e.g. investment opportunities), and the [Enterprise Europe Network](#).
- **Research exploitation model** entitles the re-utilisation of the research outputs and know-how. It is of interest to academic and research organisations, capitalising on peer-reviewed publications in terms of citations and number of downloads, and applying savvy in teaching activities and future research projects. For large industrial partners, the insights will influence medium-term strategic roadmaps.
- **Technological exploitation model** revolving around using the technological know-how acquired for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them. Research units in business organisations will use lower TRL results to trial new features in pre-commercial solutions, such as open-source components, and consulting services.
- **Co-entrepreneurship-based exploitation;** project partners acting as orchestrator/community broker to support matchmaking between industrial users (needs) and technology providers (solutions). Targets are (a) to accelerate identification of relevant industrial applications taking advantage of the SmartCorners outcomes; (b) support engagement of key partners for efficient customisation, deployment, and industrialisation of the outcomes. Community engagement will promote SmartCorners results and encourage adoption into industrial users’ portfolios, thereby increasing project outreach and acceptance.

Within these four main categories, the definition of the precise exploitation model for a given result will depend on a) the distribution of the IPR ownership among the project partners, b) the distribution of the exploitation rights (commercial and non-commercial) among the partners and c) the nature and interests of the specific owners. The exploitation strategy (individual or joint) shall focus on the approach by which the consortium (or at least some partners) will capitalise on specific high-level outputs achieved within the lifetime and ambition of the project – i.e. the Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

To ensure early take-up of exploitation in the project, the cooperation with the Horizon Results Booster has started at the point of writing this deliverable. The SmartCorners project has applied for G2M options and will cooperate with the experts of the Horizon Results Booster, benefitting from the experience and leveraging the SmartCorners exploitation strategy.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable summarizes the initial communication, dissemination and exploitation plans for the SmartCorners project. In addition to the project's general visual identity, an initial overview of the stakeholder engagement strategy, the methodology for planning and monitoring dissemination and exploitation activities and initial communication material have been presented.

The SmartCorners consortium will continuously evaluate the effectiveness of proposed methodologies and amend them where considered necessary.

9.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

There are currently no deviations for this deliverable.

10 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long text
AI	artificial intelligence
B2B	Business-to-business
CDE	Communication, dissemination, exploitation
EV	Electric vehicle
G2M	Go to market
IPR	Intellectual property
IWM	In-wheel motor
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NMPC	Nonlinear model predictive control
NNMPC	Neural network model predictive control
SME	Small and medium enterprise
WP	Work Package
XIL	X-in-the-Loop

11 Sources

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